

Analysis of defense strategies to support security operations in the Indonesia: Philippines maritime border region

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Abstract

The border area is a very strategic area for a country as a manifestation of state sovereignty, in the form of an imaginary line that separates the country from other countries on land, sea, or air that must be regulated through agreements. The border region is also a gateway to threats or disturbances from abroad that can disrupt security stability and state sovereignty. In connection with this, it is necessary to comprehensively secure border areas carried out by the TNI as a component of national defense. One of the border areas that needs attention is the RI-Philippines sea border area. The task of securing the RI-Philippines sea border area is the responsibility of the Indonesian Navy which is carried out by holding a border area security operation (Border Area Security) RI-Philippines. This research aims to analyze the RI-Philippines Border Area Security operation to maintain sovereignty and security in the Sulawesi Sea using SWOT analysis. The research uses a qualitative method with an explanatory approach that aims to find an explanation of the strategy based on intelligence data supporting the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation. The results showed that the strategy based on intelligence data greatly influenced the success of the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation.

Keywords: Intelligence Data; Operation Border Area Security RI-Philippines; SWOT Analysis

1. Introduction

Indonesia as a country with full sovereignty over its entire national jurisdiction has a very strategic geographical position, located at the crossroads between the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean, as well as between the Asian Continent and the Australian Continent. Indonesia is also one of the largest archipelagic countries in the world with a sea area of more than two-thirds of the total area of Indonesia. Indonesia has a national jurisdiction area of approximately.

7.9 km² and two-thirds of its sea area has an area of approximately 5.9 km². Indonesia's national jurisdiction consists of several islands separated by an ocean of approximately 17,504 islands. Some of the islands spread throughout Indonesia's national jurisdiction are directly adjacent to the sea and land areas of ten neighboring countries. The ten countries that border Indonesia's national jurisdiction sea areas are India, Thailand, Vietnam, Malaysia, Singapore, the Philippines, Palau Islands, Papua New Guinea, Australia, and Timor Leste (Batubara, 2016). In addition, there are 92 small outer islands, 13 of which require special attention.

The strategic value of border areas as sovereignty, the base of defense, as a basic point in the determination of territorial boundaries, Exclusive Economic Zones, and continental shelves needs special attention from the government and all components of Indonesian society. Some of the sea border areas owned by Indonesia are still in the process of

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negotiating the establishment of maritime boundaries by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. These conditions trigger conflicts over state border issues. If the region does not receive special attention from the government, it will pose a threat to the sovereignty and security of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The Indonesia-Philippines maritime border is one of ten maritime border areas between Indonesia and neighboring countries, and it has problems that have the potential to become border conflicts between the two countries in the future.

Since a long time ago, social relations between the people of the Sangihe Islands and Talaud Islands, along with the people of the Southern Philippines, have been well established. Kinship ties and traditional livelihood activities inherited from the past through family visits and commerce, exchange, and barter of goods between residents of Southern Mindanao and Nusa Utara developed into traditional cross-border trade. The needs of the people of the Sangihe Islands and Talaud Islands are more imported from the Philippines, which has a relatively closer distance to Indonesia's frontier islands (Miangas and Marore Islands) compared to other Indonesian regions. These conditions have the potential to cause problems that can trigger insecurity in the form of territorial violations, shipping violations, survey/research activities, and exploration and exploitation of natural resources. Unconducive domestic security in the southern Philippines due to tensions between the government and Moro guerrillas and the Abu Sayyaf Group (ASG) armed group has the potential to trigger piracy, smuggling of weapons and explosives from the Philippines to conflict areas in Indonesia or vice versa. The RI-Philippines sea border area is also prone to be used as an access or entry/exit route for terrorism and the Abu Sayyaf Group (ASG) armed group to Indonesia.

To avoid vulnerability in the border area, it is necessary to secure intensively by carrying out operation titles carried out by the Navy. The presence of the TNI AL Sea Task Force in the border area has a positive impact on ensuring sovereignty and security in the waters of the Sulawesi Sea, especially the North Sulawesi Sea. Efforts that have been made by the Indonesian Navy to maintain sovereignty and security in the RI-Philippines border region are by carrying out RI-Philippines Border Area Security (Border Area Security) operations involving components of the Integrated Fleet Weapon System (SSAT) both through Military Operations of War (OMP) and Military Operations Other than War (OMSP). In his book entitled "Indonesian Navy, Global Maritime Fulcrum, and ASEAN", Octavian (2019) explains that maritime security is an important indicator of how a country protects its national interests related to sovereignty, freedom of navigation, economic development, and political stability in the region (Octavian, 2019)

When faced with the area and conditions of the operating area, the strength of the defense equipment deployed is still not able to overcome all threats and violations and reach all patrol areas in the operating area. The support of valid and up-to-date intelligence data in carrying out Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations is also still not optimal. Operations are distributed to occupy patrol sectors following the Operations Plan (RO) not based on valid and up-to-date intelligence data. This condition causes the patrols carried out not to focus on patrol sectors with high vulnerability. Intelligence data support is needed to be able to determine the priority scale of patrols in selective vulnerable areas and the right way to act in overcoming threats and violations that occur.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Maritime Security Theory

Indonesia as an archipelagic country has a great responsibility for maritime security in its jurisdictional waters. Maritime security is a very complex problem at sea, for which an analysis is needed to analyze the dimensions of maritime security in terms of possible threats that may come or arise from and or through the sea to increase security against these threats. According to Schildknecht and colleagues in their book entitled "Operational Law in International Straits and Current Maritime Security Challenges," maritime security is defined as a set of security issues covering topics such as illegal fishing, security and safety in ports and onboard ships, piracy, ship refugees, terrorism at sea and weapons of mass destruction at sea (Schildknecht, Dickey, Fink and Ferris, 2018). Today, all countries generally agree that naval power plays the most important role in enhancing maritime security. However, more traditional military and military security issues are not central to maritime security. The military is one of several other tools to help enhance maritime security.

Schildknecht's (2018) security theory is reinforced by Bueger's (2020) opinion that there are four concepts to be considered in maritime security, namely sea power or naval power, marine safety, deep sea economy (blue economy) and human resilience (Schildknecht, Dickey, Fink and Ferris, 2018). The concept of sea power explains the role of the Navy, which is to protect the continuity of the state, protect sea transport routes for trade and economic improvement.

Based on the above theory explaining maritime security, it can be concluded that the strength of the Indonesian Navy is very instrumental in improving maritime security in Indonesia's national jurisdiction sea area. Related to maritime security, the Border Area Security RI- Philippines operation is one form of the Navy's role in improving maritime security in the RI- Philippines sea border area which is implemented in an operation title. The relationship between sea operations and maritime security theory is a reference that can be used by researchers in discussing the formulation of the problem of the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation to maintain sovereignty and security in the Sulawesi Sea.

2.2. Theory of Intelligence.

The success of naval operations is largely determined by the intelligence data collected before carrying out operations. Several theories of intelligence have defined intelligence in various terms, one of which defines Intelligence as a product resulting from the process of collecting, assembling, evaluating, analyzing, integrating, and interpreting all information that is successfully obtained related to national security issues (Widjajanto & Wardhani, 2008). In other words, intelligence is the essence of knowledge that attempts to make predictions by analyzing and synthesizing current information flows and provides decision-makers with a range of background projections and alternative courses of action against which policies and actions can be measured.

In terms of understanding, intelligence can be distinguished or classified into three basic definitions (Yuwono, 2011) as follows:

- Intelligence as a science is intelligence used as a method to produce early warning systems. According to Clauser (2008), intelligence is information that has been evaluated, and also states that the purpose of intelligence is to help policymakers and planners make effective decisions.
- Intelligence as security and mobilization are conducted to obtain raw materials for intelligence analysis.
- Intelligence as an organization is an entity that has a structure and system with a function to produce intelligence knowledge or information.

2.3. Research Methods

The research method used by researchers in this study is to use qualitative research methods through field research. The research approach used by researchers in carrying out research is to use an explanatory approach that aims to find an explanation of why a symptom or event occurs. In his book entitled "Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Method Approaches Fourth Edition" John W. Creswell explains that qualitative research is a method for exploring and understanding the meaning that several individuals or groups of people ascribe to social or humanitarian problems (Creswell, 2016).

Primary data obtained by researchers comes from officials who are directly involved as policymakers and implementers of Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations as resource persons. The data sources collected and processed by researchers were obtained through interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) in the form of information from interviews with sources or informants from the Navy. While secondary data is obtained through literature studies of books, documents, previous research, and official portals of related institutions. The results of data collection are used in analyzing the capabilities of defense equipment and logistical support for Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations using the SWOT method, namely Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. SWOT analysis is a strategic planning technique that aims to Determine the right strategy in the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation. SWOT analysis is carried out by evaluating the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats to determine the right strategy for improving Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations.

SWOT analysis is carried out by determining external and internal factors which can be described as follows:

- External Factors. This external factor affects the formation of Opportunities and Threats (O and T), where this factor is related to conditions that occur outside the company that influence decision-making.
- Internal Factors. This internal factor affects the formation of Strengths and Weaknesses (S and W), where this factor is related to the conditions that occur within the company, which also affects the formation of decision-making.

The strategic factor matrix known as External Strategic Faktors Analisis Summary (EFAS) and Internal Strategic Faktors Analisis Summary (IFAS) analysis is a mode used to see external strategic factors in the form of opportunities and threats and internal strategic factors in the form of opportunities and threats and internal strategic factors in the form

of strengths and weaknesses. From several factors contained in IFAS and EFAS, it can be formulated into a strategy based on the results of calculating weights, ratings, and scores.

3. Results and discussion

In the SWOT analysis, researchers identified the internal and external factors of the SWOT strategic environment using the FGD method, namely discussions with several experts who have an understanding of the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation and have been directly involved in the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation both as regulators and operators.

Table 1 Score value of weight and rating

No	Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths				
1	Strengths Intelligence data can be obtained from staff	0.850	4.5	3,825
2	Intelligence data can be obtained from Operating elements and supporting bases in the area of operations.	0.950	4.5	4,275
3	The existence of a Command Center that can present data on the situation of elements and operating areas	0.750	3.8	2,850
4	ADO data from intelligence staff and support bases in the area of operations	0.775	3.9	3,023
Total Strengths				13,973
Weaknesses				
1	Limited on-board technology to obtain	0.775	3.6	2,790
2	There is still a lack of intelligence	0.850	4.2	3,570
3	Low ability of intelligence personnel	0.850	4.5	3,825
4	Limited intelligence data supporting	0.775	3.6	2,790
Total Weaknesses				12,975
No	External Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunities				
1.	Weather forecast data from BMKG	0.775	3.4	2,635
2.	Intelligence data from side units operating in the area of operations	0.875	4.2	3,675
3.	Knowing the mode of offenses and crimes committed by the perpetrators	0.700	3.2	2,240
4.	The establishment of Maritime Information Center makes it easier to obtain intelligence data	0.800	4.1	3,280
Total Opportunities				11,830
Threats				
1.	Weather conditions in the operating area are not good	0.750	3.4	2,550
2.	Diverse types of offenses and crimes	0.675	3.3	2,228
3.	High number of offences and crimes	0.750	4.0	3,000
4.	Intelligence data from open source is invalid	0.825	4.3	3,548
Total Threats				11,325

From the results of the score calculation above, the value obtained on internal factors, namely the Strength factor of 13.973 and the Weaknesses factor of 12.975, while on external factors, namely the Opportunities factor of 11.830 and the Threats factor of 11.325. From the results of the score calculation above, the difference between each Internal and external factor can be calculated which can be used to determine the X and Y axes in the SWOT quadrant as shown in the Table below:

Table 2 Quadrant Calculation (X-axis and Y-axis)

Internal (X)	Value	External (Y)	Value
<i>Strengths</i>	13,973	Opportunities	11,830
<i>Weaknesses</i>	12,975	Threats	11,325
Difference	0,998	Difference	0,505

From the table, the results of the calculation of internal factors' strengths and Weaknesses obtained a difference value S-W of 0.998 which can be described in the SWOT quadrant as the X axis, while the results of the calculation of external factors Opportunities with and Threats obtained a difference value O-T of 0.505 which can be described in the SWOT quadrant as the Y axis so that the selected strategy can be described in the SWOT quadrant, namely in quadrant I which supports aggressive strategies. The strategy that can be formulated in quadrant I that supports an aggressive strategy is to increase strengths (strengths) by taking advantage of existing Opportunities, or in other words, an SO strategy that aims to optimize strengths to take advantage of existing Opportunities, is aggressive and is based on the comparative advantages possessed by an organization. For more details, the strategy formulation obtained from the results of quadrant calculations (X-axis and Y-axis) can be seen in Figure 1. below:

Source: Researcher's Processed Results

Figure 1 S-O - SWOT Quadrant

Based on the IFAS, EFAS tables, and quadrant calculations, the formulated strategy can be depicted in the SWOT quadrant image above, where it is known that the selected strategy is the S-O / Strengths-Opportunities strategy (supporting Aggressive strategies). The formulation of the main strategy used is the S-O strategy, namely the organization has internal factors in the form of strengths that can be improved by taking advantage of opportunities from existing external organizational factors. From the results of the SWOT strategy formulation that has been obtained, the focus of strategy formulation is to increase the strength of internal factors by utilizing opportunities from existing internal factors to formulate a good strategy in the Border Area Security RI-Filipna operation.

To make better analyses and formulate strategies, a format for analysis and formulation of strategies combined using the SWOT Matrix approach was created. The analysis format and strategy formulation can be seen in the SWOT Matrix table presented in Table 3. below:

Table 3 Swot Matrix

<p style="text-align: center;">IFAS</p> <p>EFAS</p>	<p><i>Strengths (S)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Intelligence data can be obtained from the Koarmada intelligence staff. -Intelligence data can be obtained from operating elements and supporting bases in the area of operations. -The existence of Koarmada that can present data on the situation of elements and operating areas -ADO data from Koarmada intelligence staff and supporting bases in the area of operations 	<p><i>Weaknesses (W)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Limited on-board technology to obtain intelligence data in <i>real-time</i> -There is still a lack of intelligence personnel who carry out operations -Low ability of intelligence personnel to obtain valid intelligence data -Limited intelligence data supporting operations
<p><i>Opportunities (O)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Weather forecast data from BMKG -Intelligence data from side units operating in the area of operations -Knowing the mode of offenses and crimes committed by the perpetrators -The establishment of Pusinfomar TNI makes it easier to obtain intelligence data 	<p>S101</p> <p>S102</p> <p>S103</p> <p>S104</p> <p>S201</p> <p>S202</p> <p>S203</p> <p>S204</p> <p>S301</p> <p>S302</p> <p>S303</p> <p>S304</p>	<p>W101</p> <p>W102</p> <p>W103</p> <p>W104</p> <p>W201</p> <p>W202</p> <p>W203</p> <p>W204</p> <p>W301</p> <p>W302</p> <p>W303</p> <p>W304</p>
<p><i>Threats (T)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Weather conditions in the operating area are not good -Diverse types of offenses and crimes -High number of offences and crimes -Intelligence data from open source is invalid 	<p>S1T1</p> <p>S1T2</p> <p>S1T3</p> <p>S1T4</p> <p>S2T1</p> <p>S2T2</p> <p>S2T3</p> <p>S2T4</p> <p>S3T1</p> <p>S3T2</p> <p>S3T3</p> <p>S3T4</p>	<p>W1T1</p> <p>W1T2</p> <p>W1T3</p> <p>W1T4</p> <p>W2T1</p> <p>W2T2</p> <p>W2T3</p> <p>W2T4</p> <p>W3T1</p> <p>W3T2</p> <p>W3T3</p> <p>W3T4</p>

The SWOT matrix in Table 4.8 above is the preparation of the results of the identification of internal and external factors from the influence of intelligence data on the Border Area Security RI- Philippines operation which describes the strengths and weaknesses possessed and the opportunities and threats faced in carrying out the operation. The internal and external factors are arranged and combined systematically and structured to produce four kinds of strategy formulations, namely the S-O, S-T, W-O, and W-T strategies.

Furthermore, to determine the selected strategy in the SO quadrant from several alternatives that have been formulated, the order of the strategies can be ranked as shown in Table following:

Table 4 SO Strategy Ranking

No	Strategy formulation	Final score		Results	Order
		S	O		
1	S101	3,825	2,635	10,079	-
2	S102	3,825	3,675	14,057	2
3	S103	3,825	2,240	8,568	-
4	S104	3,825	3,280	12,546	4
5	S201	4,275	2,635	11,265	5
6	S202	4,275	3,675	15,711	1
7	S203	4,275	2,240	9,576	-
8	S204	4,275	3,280	14,022	3
9	S301	2,850	2,635	7,510	-
10	S302	2,850	3,675	10,474	-
11	S303	2,850	2,240	6,384	-
12	S304	2,850	3,280	9,348	-
13	S401	3,023	2,635	7,964	-
14	S402	3,023	3,675	11,108	-
15	S403	3,023	2,240	6,770	-
16	S404	3,023	3,280	9,914	-

From the ranking of strategies using the SWOT analysis method as presented in the table above, the selected strategy is S-O/Strengths-Opportunities (supporting Aggressive strategies). Although the S-O strategy is the best alternative strategy that has the highest weighting value, it is not certain that all of these strategies can be implemented simultaneously, so it is necessary to prioritize strategies based on the following ranking:

- The priority of the selected strategy is S2-02 with a score value of 15,711.
- The second priority of the selected strategy is S1-02 with a score of 14.057.
- The third priority selected strategy is S2-04 with a score value of 14.022.
- The fourth priority of the selected strategy is S1-04 with a score of 12.546.
- The fifth priority of the selected strategy is S2-01 with a score value of 11.265.

3.1. SWOT Decision Making

Based on the analysis using the SWOT method above, the results of strategy priorities that support aggressive strategies have been obtained. From the SWOT matrix table, if formulated with the selected strategic priorities, the strategy formulation to improve the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation is obtained by taking into account the IFAS and EFAS factor components in the SWOT matrix as follows:

- The formulation of the first strategy S2-02 is utilizing intelligence data obtained from operating elements and supporting bases in the area of operations and coordinating with side units operating in the area of operations to obtain intelligence data to support Border Area Security RI- Filipina operations.
- The formulation of the second S102 strategy is to utilize intelligence data obtained from the Koarmada II intelligence staff by supplementing intelligence data from side units operating in the area of operations so that valid intelligence data is obtained. With valid intelligence data, the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation can be carried out effectively and efficiently.

- The formulation of the third strategy S2-04 is to utilize intelligence data obtained from operating elements and supporting bases in the area of operation, supported by intelligence data obtained from the analysis of Maritime Information Center so as to obtain valid and up-to-date data supporting Border Area Security operations.
- The formulation of the S1-04 strategy is to utilize intelligence data obtained from Koarmada intelligence staff complemented by intelligence data obtained from the analysis of Maritime Information Center so as to obtain valid and up-to-date intelligence data supporting Border Area Security operations.
- The formulation of strategy S2-01 is to utilize intelligence data from side units operating in the area of operations complemented by weather forecast data from BMKG as a consideration in the deployment of elements.

From the five strategy formulations above, based on the IFAS and EFAS considerations that have been analyzed, a decision can be made regarding the best strategy that can be used in the Border Area Security RI-Filipina operation regarding the influence of intelligence data is "Utilising intelligence data obtained from operating elements and supporting bases in the operating area and coordinating with side units operating in the operating area to obtain intelligence data to support Border Area Security RI-Filipina operations".

3.2. Efforts made according to theory and selected strategies

For operations to be carried out effectively, efficiently, and successfully, data or information support is needed in an operation. Data and information support in the necessary operations is in the form of data or intelligence information about the weather, terrain, and enemy conditions. Operation Border Area Security RI-Philippines is one of the forms of OMSP, namely securing the border area, so it is necessary to support valid data and intelligence information related to weather conditions in the operating area, types of violations and crimes that occur, and data or information related to the state of the people of the two countries in the border area. The number and complexity of the problems found in the RI-Philippines border region require more serious handling, so it is necessary to deploy operations in the sea border area and intelligence operations carried out in Indonesia and the Philippines by placing agents there.

The influence of intelligence data on operations is by the theory of intelligence in Andi Widjayanto's book, which defines Intelligence as a product resulting from the process of collecting, assembling, evaluating, analyzing, integrating, and interpreting all information that is successfully obtained related to national security issues (Widjajanto & Wardhani, 2008). Intelligence is the essence of knowledge that attempts to make predictions by analyzing and synthesizing current information flows, as well as providing decision-makers with background projections and alternative courses of action against which policies and actions can be measured. Based on the theory of intelligence, it can be explained that the Border Area Security RI- Philippines operation can be carried out effectively efficiently, and successfully if it is supported by intelligence data obtained from the results of intelligence operations.

Decision-making in the implementation of Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations can be carried out precisely and precisely based on data and information obtained from the results of intelligence operations. The results of research conducted by researchers through interviews and FGDs with several resource persons who have been processed using NVivo 12 software obtained the results that intelligence data is very important in the success of an operation. Border Area Security operations carried out so far have not been optimally supported by sufficient and valid intelligence data. This condition is research data based on the results of interviews and FGDs with resource persons who found problems when carrying out or observing Border Area Security RI- Philippines operations. The findings of prominent problems related to intelligence data supporting Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations are often invalid data provided to Border Area Security RI- RI-Philippines operation elements. The data provided is more often in the form of analytical data obtained from open sources and media by utilizing information technology from the internet. To obtain valid intelligence data from data analysis results from open sources and information media, it is necessary to support data sourced from operating elements and supporting bases in the operating area as well as side units that operate in the RI-Philippines border area both from agents and ILOs assigned in the Philippines.

Intelligence data required to support the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation is data in the form of operating area conditions such as weather conditions, terrain, and threats in the form of violations and crimes that occur.

For violations and crimes that occur in the RI-Philippines sea border region, valid data is needed. Based on data obtained from previous operations, data related to the types of violations and crimes that often occur in the RI-Philippines border area are IUU Fishing violations. IUU Fishing violations in this border area have also been researched by Yoshua Jaya Edy (2017) with the title of his research, *Illegal Fishing Network at the Indonesia-Philippines border*. In his research, Yoshua specifically discusses the mode of IUU Fishing violations that occur in the RI- Philippines border

area. There is a relevance between the results of the research conducted by the researcher and the previous researcher, Yoshua Jaya Edy, so the type of violation that still occurs in the RI-Philippines border area to date is IUU Fishing violation.

IUU Fishing violations greatly affect the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation carried out by the Navy. If the number of IUU Fishing violations increases, the Border Area Security RI-Filipina operation must also be increased both by increasing the number of elements and increasing the time of operation. The influence of the type of IUU Fishing violations on Border Area Security RI- Filipina operations is also by the theory of maritime security put forward by Schildknecht and friends in his book entitled "Operational Law in International Straits and Current Maritime Security Challenges" maritime security is defined as a series of security issues covering topics such as illegal fishing, security and safety in ports and on board ships, piracy, ship refugees, terrorism at sea and weapons of mass destruction at sea. Operation Border Area Security RI- Philippines is one of the efforts to maintain sovereignty and security at sea, especially in the RI-Philippines border area and the Sulawesi Sea to face all forms of threats and violations following the theory of maritime security put forward by Schildknecht and friends.

Referring to the intelligence theory, previous research, and maritime security theory above, it can be seen that intelligence data is very influential on the RI-Philippines Border Area Security operation. The RI-Philippines operation which is held with one of its objectives is to crack down on violations and crimes that occur in the RI-Philippines border area as an effort to solve problems that include topics such as illegal fishing, security and safety in ports and on ships, piracy, ship refugees, terrorism at sea and weapons of mass destruction at sea following maritime security theory. To be able to address security issues based on maritime security theory, comprehensive and valid intelligence data is required. However, the current condition is that the intelligence data supporting the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation presented is still insufficient and invalid. Based on the results of strategy formulation using SWOT, several efforts can be made through the strategy of utilizing intelligence data obtained from operating elements and supporting bases in the operating area and coordinating with side units operating in the operating area to obtain intelligence data to support Border Area Security RI-Filipina operations, among others:

Placing intelligence personnel and Navy personnel who have competence in the field of intelligence in elements that carry out Border Area Security RI-Philippines operations. These personnel are expected to periodically carry out data collection and update data collected by direct observation in the area of operation both while at sea and when docked at the base so that valid intelligence data is obtained and can be used by other operating elements carrying out operations in the RI-Filipina border area.

Equip intelligence personnel serving at supporting bases in the area of operations with the necessary facilities and infrastructure to carry out data collection and mobilization with the local community so that comprehensive and valid intelligence data can be used by ST Border Area Security RI-Filipina operating elements and other operating elements that are equally carrying out operations in the border area.

Establish cooperation and coordination with side units outside the Navy operating in the RI-Philippines border area to complement intelligence data obtained from the Koarmada II intelligence staff, operating elements, and supporting bases in the operating area. The more intelligence data collected which is then analyzed, it provides

Comprehensive and valid data and information so that operations can be carried out optimally, effectively, and efficiently and succeed according to plan.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of qualitative research that has been carried out through the analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) to the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation, it can be concluded that:

First, the border security operation (Border Area Security) of RI-Philippines that is currently implemented is still not optimal when faced with the vast area of operation that is the responsibility and the ability of operationalized defense equipment both in terms of quantity and quality. Valid and comprehensive intelligence data supporting operations is one of the factors affecting the success of the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operation. With valid and comprehensive intelligence data, the operations carried out can focus on addressing priority threats of violations and crimes in the RI-Philippines sea border area following the intelligence data provided.

Secondly, the intelligence data required in supporting the border security operations (Border Area Security) of RI-Philippines is data or information in the form of operating areas such as weather conditions, terrain, and threats in the form of violations or crimes in the RI-Philippines sea border area. These intelligence data will become valid and

comprehensive intelligence data if obtained from operating elements and supporting bases in the operating area as well as the results of coordination with side units operating in the RI-Philippines border area. The current condition of the valid and comprehensive intelligence data has not been obtained by the Border Area Security RI-Philippines operating elements that are carrying out operations due to the absence of intelligence personnel assignments in the operating elements, limited intelligence personnel and infrastructure facilities at supporting bases to carry out intelligence data collection supporting operations and no or coordination between the Navy intelligence task force and side units that are carrying out operations in the RI-Philippines border region.

Third, some efforts that can be made to obtain valid and comprehensive intelligence data supporting Border Area Security RI-Filipina operations are by placing intelligence personnel and Navy personnel who have competence in the field of intelligence in the elements carrying out Border Area Security RI-Filipina operations; equipping personnel and supporting base intelligence infrastructure facilities in the operating area to carry out data collection and raising with the local community; and establishing cooperation and coordination with side units outside the Navy operating in the RI-Filipina border area to complement existing intelligence data.

Compliance with ethical standards

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